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PERCEIVED INFLUENCE OF LIBRARY RESOURCES ON LECTURERS' TEACHING EFFICIENCY IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN RIVERS STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the perceived influence of library resources on lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State. Three objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of 7,023 lecturers from the three public universities in Rivers State, which comprised of University of Port Harcourt 4,213, Rivers State University 1800, and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education 1010. Taro Yamane was used to determine a sample size of 376 lecturers from the population of the three Universities while adopting proportionate stratified random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled "Perceived Influence of Library Resources on Lecturers' Teaching Efficiency Questionnaire". The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by two experts in the Department of Educational Management, and one from Measurement and Evaluation, Department of Educational Foundations; all in the Faculty of Education, Rivers State University. Cronbach Alpha method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument to obtain reliability coefficients of .81, .75 and .85. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics at .05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that, availability of current textbooks, access to scholarly journals and subscription to online academic databases influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that, university administrators and government stakeholders should increase funding allocations for the procurement of up-to-date academic resources, including current textbooks, peer-reviewed journals, reference materials, and electronic databases.

Keywords: Library Resources, Lecturers, Teaching Efficiency, Public Universities.

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INTRODUCTION

In the evolving landscape of higher education, library resources play a pivotal role in supporting academic activities, particularly teaching, research and learning. Libraries are widely recognized as the academic heartbeat of universities as they serve as repositories of knowledge and platforms for scholarly exploration. For lecturers, especially in public universities, access to relevant, current, and diverse library resources is essential for delivering effective teaching. Teaching efficiency encompasses lecturers' ability to communicate subject matter clearly, update course content regularly and utilize innovative pedagogical strategies. These outcomes are largely dependent on the quality and availability of library resources such as textbooks, academic journals, electronic databases, and multimedia instructional materials (Iloanusi & Okolie, 2021). Without adequate access to these resources, lecturers may struggle to maintain content relevance, hindering the overall quality of education.

Library resources refer to the comprehensive collection of academic materials and services provided by university libraries to support teaching, learning and research. These resources include print and digital textbooks, scholarly journals, e-books, electronic databases, audiovisual materials, theses, dissertations and reference works such as dictionaries and encyclopedias (Okon & Bassey, 2022). In addition to physical materials, library resources also encompass online repositories, bibliographic tools, instructional guides and user support services. These resources are integral to lecturers' instructional duties, as they provide the scholarly foundation needed for lesson planning, curriculum delivery and evidence-based teaching. Access to a robust and well organized library collection allows lecturers to update course content, integrate current research findings and address diverse student learning needs (Agboola & Bamigboye, 2021). Therefore, library resources serve as both informational and pedagogical assets that enhance teaching effectiveness and academic productivity. The indicators of library resources that influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities include: availability of current textbooks, access to scholarly journals and subscription to online academic databases and so on.

Availability of current textbooks refers to the consistent provision and accessibility of recently published and up-to-date instructional materials that align with contemporary academic curricula. These textbooks contain the latest theories, empirical findings, models and practices relevant to various disciplines and fields of study. In public universities, especially within resource-constrained contexts like Nigeria, the presence of current textbooks in university libraries play a vital role in shaping the quality and relevance of academic instruction. Lecturers, having access to updated textbooks enhance their capacity to plan lessons effectively, provide students with accurate knowledge and integrate contemporary developments into their teaching (Adewuyi & Akinade, 2023). Textbooks that reflect recent advancements in a discipline help lecturers' to maintain academic credibility and engage students with current real-world issues and solutions.

The influence of current textbooks on teaching efficiency is evident in the lecturer's ability to deliver well-informed, engaging and research-based instruction. Teaching efficiency involves more than delivering content, it includes critical thinking, content relevance, timely updates and the ability to respond to emerging questions from students. Current textbooks serve as authoritative references that support evidence-based teaching, minimize reliance on outdated concepts, and enable lecturers to design innovative and responsive course content. When public universities prioritize the acquisition of new editions of textbooks, they empower lecturers to

keep pace with global academic trends, thereby raising instructional standards (Yakubu & Dauda, 2022). Conversely, limited access to current textbooks often results in content stagnation, reduced academic engagement and suboptimal learning outcomes. Therefore, the strategic provision of updated textbooks in university libraries is crucial to sustaining high-quality teaching and learning experiences in public higher education institutions.

Access to scholarly journals refers to the ability of lecturers to retrieve peer-reviewed, discipline specific publications that contain original research, critical analyses, theoretical developments, and empirical findings. These journals are vital tools for academic engagement, enabling lecturers to stay current with advancements in their fields and incorporate cutting-edge knowledge into their teaching. In the context of public universities, especially in Nigeria, access to scholarly journals, both in print and digital formats, empowers lecturers to align their course content with global academic standards and enhance the intellectual rigor of their classroom instruction (Akinbode & Salami, 2023). Journals do not only offer current information but also expose lecturers to a variety of perspectives and methodologies that can enrich teaching practices and stimulate students' critical thinking abilities.

The influence of scholarly journal access on lecturers' teaching efficiency is profound. Efficient teaching demands that lecturers possess updated knowledge and the ability to deliver it in a manner that is evidence-based and contextually relevant. When lecturers access scholarly journals regularly, they are more likely to integrate recent research findings, cite authoritative sources, and adopt innovative pedagogical strategies. This fosters credibility in the classroom and enhances student engagement with contemporary academic discourse (Olawale & Okpara, 2022). On the contrary, limited access to journals restricts lecturers to outdated information, diminishing their ability to offer timely and impactful instruction. Therefore, sustained access to scholarly journals through well-funded university libraries and electronic databases is crucial to fostering a high standard of teaching efficiency in public universities.

Subscription to online academic databases refers to the institutional access provided by universities to digital platforms that host scholarly journals, e-books, conference proceedings, and other academic publications. These databases, such as JSTOR, ScienceDirect, ProQuest, EBSCOhost, and SpringerLink, offer lecturers a vast repository of peer-reviewed materials and research tools essential for academic work. In public universities, such subscriptions are critical for enabling faculty members to retrieve high-quality and current information needed for lecture content development, course updates and academic referencing. Access to these databases empower lecturers to stay informed about trends and breakthroughs in their disciplines, thus promoting evidence-based teaching (Nwachukwu & Okafor, 2023). With such resources readily available, lecturers are better equipped to engage students with up-to-date information, case studies and comparative insights from global academic discourse.

The influence of these subscriptions on teaching efficiency is both strategic and transformative. Teaching efficiency in higher education is not only measured by knowledge delivery but also by the ability to critically engage learners with current and relevant scholarly information. Through the use of academic databases, lecturers can integrate contemporary findings into their curriculum, design assignments based on recent research and expose students to diverse academic perspectives. This enhances content quality, fosters critical thinking and bridges the gap between theory and real-world application. Moreover, online databases support interdisciplinary teaching and continuous professional development, making it easier for lecturers to update their skills and adapt to emerging trends in pedagogy (Mohammed & Ibrahim, 2022). In the absence of such resources, lecturers may rely on outdated or limited materials,

which can reduce the depth, accuracy and relevance of instructional delivery in public universities.

Lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities refers to the capacity of academic staff to effectively deliver course content, facilitate student learning, and achieve defined instructional objectives using optimal time, resources and pedagogical methods. It encompasses the lecturer's ability to plan lectures, engage students actively, communicate ideas clearly, assess learning outcomes and adapt teaching strategies based on student needs and academic goals. In the context of public universities, especially within developing countries like Nigeria, teaching efficiency is pivotal for improving educational standards, fostering critical thinking, and preparing students for the demands of the global workforce (Babalola & Olayemi, 2022). Teaching efficiency also entails the integration of technological tools, access to updated academic resources and ongoing self-improvement by lecturers through training, research, and professional development.

Moreover, the effectiveness of teaching in public universities is often measured by students' academic performance, feedback, classroom engagement and knowledge application after graduation. Efficient lecturers demonstrate mastery of their subject areas, manage classroom dynamics effectively and incorporate innovative techniques such as problem-based learning, blended learning and collaborative instruction to enhance student participation (Idris & Danjuma, 2023). Inadequate infrastructure, limited access to up-to-date teaching materials and high student-to-lecturer ratios can impair teaching efficiency in Nigerian public universities. Therefore, promoting teaching efficiency requires not only the personal commitment of lecturers but also institutional support through provision of resources, enabling policies, and performance evaluation systems (Ibrahim & Balogun, 2022).

The digital age has transformed traditional libraries into hybrid knowledge hubs that combine physical and digital materials to meet the expanding academic needs of lecturers. With the integration of electronic databases, institutional repositories and open access journals, libraries now provide broader and more efficient access to knowledge (Ogunniyi & Ojo, 2022). In public universities in Rivers State, such as the University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State University, and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, library resources are expected to support lecturers' instructional activities by providing current scholarly materials, teaching guides, research reports and multimedia tools. However, persistent challenges such as poor funding, inadequate internet infrastructure, limited subscriptions to electronic resources, and insufficient library staffing often undermine the availability and effective utilization of these essential academic assets (Nwokocha & Udo-Anyanwu, 2020).

Furthermore, the effectiveness of library resources in enhancing teaching efficiency lies not just in their availability but also in their accessibility and relevance to lecturers' course content. A well-resourced library enables lecturers to stay abreast of recent developments in their disciplines, align their lectures with global best practices and encourage evidence-based instruction. Additionally, it promotes academic integrity by facilitating proper referencing and discouraging plagiarism. In contrast, inadequate or outdated resources can limit a lecturer's ability to provide up-to-date knowledge, resulting in a less engaging and intellectually stimulating classroom environment (Emezie & Nwaohiri, 2022). Therefore, the alignment between a university's library investment and the teaching needs of its faculty is critical to achieving academic excellence.

Teaching efficiency among university lecturers also depends on their ability to integrate diverse learning materials into their pedagogical practices. Access to a variety of library

resources such as subject-specific encyclopedias, research handbooks, audiovisual content and instructional software enhance lecturers' capacity to adapt to different student learning styles and course delivery methods. In public universities where large student population and limited physical facilities are common, library resources can bridge gaps in instructional delivery by offering self-directed learning materials that supplement classroom teaching. Moreover, the support provided by professional librarians through user education and research assistance further empowers lecturers to maximize these resources (Olise, 2021). Thus, the library's contribution to teaching efficiency extends beyond content provision to include strategic academic support services. Given the increasing demand for quality teaching in Nigerian higher education, it becomes imperative to investigate how library resources influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State. Understanding the extent to which lecturers utilize library resources, the challenges they encounter and the support systems available will provide insights for improving academic service delivery.

Statement of the Problem

In the contemporary university system, library resources are fundamental to enhancing lecturers' teaching effectiveness and efficiency, as they provide the intellectual tools necessary for course content development, knowledge delivery and pedagogical innovation. However, in many public universities in Rivers State, Nigeria, there are growing concerns about the adequacy, accessibility and utilization of library resources, which may be limiting lecturers' instructional efficiency. Many academic libraries still grapple with outdated materials, inadequate collections in key disciplines and a lack of recent publications needed to support modern curricula (Yakubu & Dauda, 2022). These inadequacies hinder lecturers from accessing relevant teaching materials, incorporating recent scholarly perspectives into lectures and engaging students with current knowledge trends.

Furthermore, the integration of digital resources in university libraries remains largely insufficient or underutilized due to infrastructural challenges such as poor internet connectivity, limited access to licensed databases and irregular power supply. This technological gap does not only reduce lecturers' access to electronic journals, e-books, and academic databases but also affects their ability to engage in blended and technology-driven teaching methods (Adewuyi & Akinade, 2023). Without strong support from well-equipped and efficiently managed libraries, lecturers are often left to rely on personal materials, outdated textbooks or unreliable internet sources, which may compromise the depth, quality and scholarly relevance of their teaching (Olawale & Okpara, 2022). These limitations could also diminish lecturers' confidence, reduce student engagement, and impair learning outcomes.

In spite of the crucial role of libraries in enhancing teaching efficiency, there appears to be limited empirical evidence assessing the influence of library resources on lecturers' teaching efficiency within the context of public universities in Rivers State. This knowledge gap creates uncertainty for university administrators and policymakers aiming to improve academic quality and instructional productivity. Hence, this researcher investigated the perceived influence of library resources on lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate perceived influence of library resources on lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

- Determine the extent to which availability of current textbooks influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State.
- Find out the extent to which access to scholarly journals influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State.
- Ascertain the extent to which subscription to online academic databases influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- To what extent does availability of current textbooks influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State?
- To what extent does access to scholarly journals influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State?
- To what extent does subscription to online academic databases influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following null hypotheses tested at .05 level of significance:

- There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female lecturers on the extent to which availability of current textbooks influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State.
- There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female lecturers on the extent to which access to scholarly journals influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State.
- There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female lecturers on the extent to which subscription to online academic databases influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study investigated the influence of library resources on lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study consisted of 7,023 lecturers from the three universities in Rivers State, which comprised of University of Port Harcourt - 4,213, Rivers State University - 1800, and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education - 1,010. Taro Yamane was used to determine the sample size of 376 lecturers from the three

Universities, drawn from the population using proportionate stratified random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled “Perceived Influence of Library Resources on Lecturers’ Teaching Efficiency Questionnaire (PILRLTEQ)”.

The questionnaire consisted of two sections namely section A and B. Section A of the questionnaire was used to generate demographic information while section B consisted of questionnaire items addressing the research questions of the study. This section of the questionnaire was structured using a five-point summated rating response scale of: Very High Extent (VHE) = 5 points, High Extent (HE) = 4 points, Moderate Extent (ME) = 3Points, Low Extent (LE) = 2 points, Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1 point. The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by two experts in the Department of Educational Management and one from Measurement and Evaluation; Department of Educational Foundations, all in Rivers State University.

The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha method to obtain reliability indexes of .81, .75 and .85. A total of 376 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and all were successfully retrieved, yielding a 100% response and retrieval rates. The distribution and retrieval of copies of the questionnaire were facilitated by two research assistants. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while t-test statistics was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance. Criterion mean for decisions made was 3.00. Mean values between 3.00 and 5.00 were said to be ‘High Extent’ while below 3.00 were denoted ‘Low Extent’. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted when the t-calculated value was greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. On the contrary, the null hypothesis was also accepted and the alternate hypotheses rejected when the reverse is the case.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: To what extent does availability of current textbooks influence lecturers’ teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean ratings of male and female lecturers on the extent to which availability of current textbooks influence their teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State

S/N	Questionnaire Items	Lecturers				Average	SD	Remark
		Male = 173		Female = 203				
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂			
1.	Current textbooks ensure that lecturers teach content that aligns with the latest developments in their field.	3.65	0.89	3.69	0.87	3.67	0.88	HE
2.	Access to updated textbooks provide lecturers with a reliable foundation for structuring lectures, developing instructional materials, and delivering lessons more confidently and coherently.	4.19	1.33	4.20	1.29	4.19	1.31	HE
3.	Current textbooks often incorporate clearer explanations, updated diagrams, and contemporary examples that help lecturers explain complex concepts more effectively to students.	3.00	0.68	3.02	0.67	3.01	0.68	HE

4.	Modern textbooks are usually grounded in recent research findings, allowing lecturers to integrate scholarly insights into their teaching practices.	3.07	0.78	3.09	0.78	3.08	0.79	HE
5.	Lecturers using up-to-date textbooks can assign relevant readings, case studies, and discussion questions that better engage students and foster critical thinking.	3.00	0.75	3.03	0.74	3.02	0.75	HE
Aggregate Mean and SD.		3.38	0.89	3.41	0.87	3.39	0.88	HE

Table 1 in response to research question 1 showed the following mean scores for questionnaire items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 as 3.65, 4.19, 3.00, 3.07 and 3.00 with standard deviations of 0.89, 1.33, 0.68, 0.78 and 0.75 for male lecturers while for the female lecturers the mean scores were 3.69, 4.20, 3.02, 3.09 and 3.03 with standard deviation of 0.87, 1.29, 0.67, 0.78 and 0.74. Furthermore, the mean set representing the average mean scores for both male and female lecturers were 3.67, 4.19, 3.01, 3.08 and 3.02; with standard deviation of 0.88, 1.31, 0.68, 0.79 and 0.75 respectively. The readings which were higher than the criterion mean of 3.00 indicated that to a high extent availability of current textbooks influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: To what extent does scholarly journals influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean ratings of male and female lecturers on the extent to which scholarly journals influence their teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State

S/N	Items	Lecturers				Average	SD.	Remark
		Male = 173		Female = 203				
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	StD ₂			
6.	Scholarly journals provide lecturers with access to the latest research findings, allowing them to integrate up-to-date information into lectures and course materials.	3.70	0.88	3.75	0.84	3.73	0.86	HE
7.	With access to peer-reviewed journal articles, lecturers can adopt evidence based teaching strategies, enhancing the academic quality and credibility of their instruction.	4.35	1.16	4.41	1.11	4.38	1.14	VHE
8.	Journals offer insights into emerging topics, theories, and debates that lecturers can use to revise and enrich course outlines and reading lists.	3.68	1.61	3.74	1.48	3.71	1.54	HE
9.	Lecturers with access to journals are better equipped to guide students in their research projects and theses with updated literature and research trends.	3.57	0.93	3.63	0.82	3.60	0.92	HE
10.	Being informed by scholarly literature allows lecturers to speak with confidence and authority on academic issues, enhancing their professional image and classroom influence.	3.72	0.85	3.77	0.90	3.75	0.83	HE
Aggregate Mean and SD.		3.80	1.17	3.86	1.0	4.56	1.06	VHE

Table 2 in response to research question 2 had the following opinion scores for both male and female lecturers. Mean scores for male lecturers in response to questionnaire items 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 were 3.70, 4.35, 3.68, 3.57 and 3.72 with standard deviations of 0.88, 1.16, 1.61, 0.93 and 0.85 while the mean scores of the female lecturers were 3.75, 4.41, 3.74, 3.63 and 3.77 with standard deviation of 0.84, 1.11, 1.48, 0.90 and 0.82. Furthermore, the mean set representing the average mean scores for both male and female lecturers were 3.73, 4.38, 3.71, 3.60 and 3.75; with standard deviation of 0.86, 1.14, 1.54, 0.92 and 0.83 respectively. The readings which were higher than the criterion mean of 3.00 indicated that to a high extent that scholarly journals influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State.

Research Question 3: To what extent does subscription to online academic databases influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in Public Universities in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean ratings of male and female lecturers on the extent to which subscription to online academic databases influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State

S/N	Items	Lecturers				Average	SD.	Rmk.
		Male = 173 \bar{X}_1	SD ₁	Female = 203 \bar{X}_2	SD ₂			
11	Subscription to academic databases grant lecturers' immediate access to a wide range of scholarly materials; this enhancing their knowledge base and teaching content.	4.30	1.24	4.36	1.18	4.33	1.21	VHE
12	Lecturers can incorporate the most recent research and global best practices into their teaching, ensuring that course content remains current and aligned with evolving academic standards.	4.54	1.02	4.56	1.01	4.55	1.01	VHE
13	Access to global pedagogical research through databases help lecturers adopt and adapt innovative, student-centered teaching strategies that foster deep learning.	3.48	0.84	3.51	0.81	3.48	0.83	HE
14	Lecturers can integrate research findings directly into their lessons, promoting a strong linkage between research and teaching that enhances students' analytical skills.	3.52	0.90	3.51	0.87	3.52	0.89	HE
15	Lecturers can guide undergraduate and postgraduate students more effectively in research activities, referencing current and credible materials found in databases.	4.69	0.77	4.71	0.73	4.70	0.75	VHE
Aggregate Mean and SD.		3.91	0.96	4.12	0.92	4.12	0.94	VHE

Table 3, in response to research question 3 had the following opinion scores for both male and female lecturers. Mean scores for the male lecturers in response to questionnaire items 11, 12, 13, 14 and 15 were 4.30, 4.54, 3.48, 3.52 and 4.69 with standard deviations of 1.24, 1.02, 0.84, 0.90 and 0.77 while the mean scores of the female lecturers were 4.36, 4.56, 3.48, 3.51 and 4.71 with standard deviation of 1.18, 1.01, 0.81, 0.87 and 0.73. Furthermore, the mean set representing the average mean scores for both male and female lecturers were 4.33, 4.55, 3.48, 3.52 and 4.70; with standard deviation of 1.21, 1.01, 0.83, 0.89 and 0.75 respectively. The readings which were higher than the criterion mean of 3.00 indicated that to a high extent

subscription to online academic databases influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State.

Test of Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean opinion scores of male and female lecturers on the extent to which availability of current textbooks influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State.

Table 4: t-test analysis of difference on the extent to which availability of current textbooks influence male and female lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD.	Df	t-cal	t-crit	LS	Decision
Male Lecturers	173	3.38	0.89	374	0.89	±1.96	0.05	Accepted
Female lecturers	203	3.41	0.87					

The result on Tale 4 showed a t-calculated value of 0.89 which was less than the t-critical value of ±1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 374. Since the t-calculated (0.89) was less than the t-critical (±1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted which states that, there is no significant difference in the mean opinion scores of male and female lecturers on the extent to which availability of current textbooks influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean opinion scores of male and female lecturers on the extent to which access to scholarly journals influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State.

Table 5: t-test analysis of difference between the mean opinion scores of male and female lecturers on the extent to which access to scholarly journals influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD.	Df	t-cal	t-crit	LS	Decision
Male Lecturers	173	3.80	1.17	374	0.77	±1.96	0.05	Accepted
Female lecturers	203	3.86	1.03					

Table 5 above showed a t-calculated value of 0.77 which was less than the t-critical value of ±1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 374. Since the t-calculated (0.77) was less than the t-critical (±1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted which stated that there is no significant difference in the mean opinion scores of male and female lecturers on the extent to which scholarly journals influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in Public Universities in Rivers State.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference in the mean opinion scores of male and female lecturers on the extent to which subscription to online academic databases influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in Public Universities in Rivers State.

Table 6: t-test analysis of difference between the mean opinion scores of male and female lecturers on the extent subscription to which online academic databases influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	LS	Decision
Male Lecturers	173	3.91	0.96	374	0.82	± 1.96	0.05	Accepted
Female lecturers	203	4.12	0.92					

The result on Table 6, showed a t-calculated value of 0.82 which was less than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 374. Since the t-calculated (0.82) was less than the t-critical (± 1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted which stated that there is no significant difference in the mean opinion scores of male and female lecturers on the extent subscription to online academic databases influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION

Findings on Research Question 1 on Table 1 showed grand mean scores of 3.38 and 3.39 (for male and female lecturers) which were above the criterion mean of 3.00. Correspondingly, Hypothesis 1 on 4 further showed a t-calculated value of 0.89 which was less than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 374. Since the t-calculated (0.89) was less than the t-critical (± 1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference in the mean opinion scores of male and female lecturers on the extent to which availability of current textbooks influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State. The findings are in tandem with Adewuyi and Akinade (2023), who opined that lecturers' who have access to updated textbooks enhance their capacity to plan lessons effectively, provide students with accurate knowledge and integrate contemporary developments into their teaching. Also, textbooks that reflect recent advancements in a discipline help lecturers' maintain academic credibility and engage students with current real world issues and solutions. Similarly, Ndebele et al. (2022) asserted that the availability of current textbooks is crucial for effective teaching, as it enables lecturers to stay abreast of contemporary issues and methodologies in their fields, thereby improving teaching efficiency.

Findings on Research Question 2 on Table 2 showed grand mean scores of 3.80 and 4.56 (for both male and female lecturers) which were above the criterion mean of 3.00. Furthermore, result on Table 4 showed a t-calculated value of 0.77 which was less than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 374. Since the t-calculated (0.77) was less than the t-critical (± 1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted which stated that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion scores of male and female lecturers on the extent to which scholarly journals influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State. This result corroborates with Akinbode and Salami (2023), which emphasized that, access to scholarly journals, both in print and digital formats, empower lecturers to align their course content with global academic standards and enhance the intellectual rigor of their classroom instruction. Journals do not only offer current information but also expose lecturers' to a variety of perspectives and methodologies that could enrich teaching practices and stimulate students' critical thinking abilities.

Findings on Research Question 3 on Table 3 showed grand mean scores of 3.91 and 4.12 (for male and female lecturers respectively) which were above the criterion mean of 3.00; which indicated that subscription to academic online databases influence lecturers teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State. The result on Hypothesis 3 on Table 6 had a t-calculated value of 0.81 which was less than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 at .05 level of significance and with a degree of freedom of 374. Since the t-calculated (0.82) was less than the t-critical (± 1.96), the null hypothesis was accepted which stated that, there is no significant difference in the mean opinion scores of male and female lecturers on the extent subscription to online academic databases influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State. The findings were in agreement with Nwachukwu and Okafor (2023) who opined that subscriptions are critical for enabling faculty members to retrieve high-quality and current information needed for lecture content development, course updates, and academic referencing. Access to these databases empowers lecturers to stay informed about trends and breakthroughs in their disciplines, thus promoting evidence-based teaching. With such resources readily available, lecturers are better equipped to engage students with up-to-date information, case studies, and comparative insights from global academic discourse. Iroaganachi and Izuagbe (2019) further asserted that access to online databases enhance lecturers' ability to source recent research, update course materials and incorporate contemporary global perspectives thereby boosting teaching efficiency.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers concluded that, availability of current textbooks, access to scholarly journals and Subscription to online academic databases influence lecturers' teaching efficiency in public universities in Rivers State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made for the study that:

- University administrators and government stakeholders should increase funding allocations for the procurement of up-to-date academic resources, including current textbooks, peer reviewed journals, reference materials, and electronic databases. Digital resources should be made available in university libraries (such as e-books, institutional repositories) while access to international research databases (e.g., JSTOR, ScienceDirect, and SpringerLink) should be encouraged as they are essential in supporting contemporary teaching methods and academic content delivery. Also, an enhanced infrastructure, such as improved Wi-Fi access and digital cataloging systems, should be made available in universities as to enable lecturers to retrieve relevant materials more efficiently and integrate them effectively into their teaching practices.
- There should be regular capacity-building workshops and training sessions to equip lecturers with the necessary skills for efficient utilization of library resources, especially digital and online tools. This will help bridge the gap between resource availability and optimal usage. Lecturers need to be trained on advanced information retrieval strategies, citation management tools and the integration of research outputs into curriculum

delivery as this will aid them to access scholarly journals which will influence their teaching efficiency.

- Universities should maximally subscribe to online academic databases in their libraries to enhance teaching efficiency of their lecturers. This could be effectively implemented through structured monitoring and evaluation (M&E) systems to track the usage of library resources by academic staff. These systems can help identify underused resources, evaluate user satisfaction and generate actionable data for strategic decision-making. Feedback from lecturers should be periodically collected to ensure that the library is meeting their academic and teaching needs. Furthermore, establishing resource usage metrics and linking them to teaching outcomes may encourage greater accountability and drive improvements in the quality and relevance of library services.

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